

Advancing interpretable cancer gene identification via width scaling graph representation learning

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Abstract

Graph representation learning has emerged as a promising avenue for identifying cancer genes (CGs), but its application remains limited by depth scalability, heterophilic gene interactions, and insufficient interpretability. Here, we present CGMap, an interpretable graph neural network that reframes serial hierarchical information flow into a width-oriented parallel architecture, enabling localization of gene associations at arbitrary distances. By constructing hop-specific propagation channels guided by shortest-path structure and quantifying gene cooperativity via global path diffusion, CGMap yields virtual interactions that can be traced back to regulatory routes to support interpretation. This design broadens the receptive field to spatially dispersed CGs under heterophily, while remaining computationally lightweight. Experimental results show that CGMap consistently outperforms existing baselines and prioritizes 70 reliable CGs, including novel candidates absent from established databases. Importantly, *in vitro* loss-of-function assays support their pro-malignant roles in multiple cancer cell lines. In essence, CGmap establishes a scalable and interpretable graph learning paradigm for exploring CGs and potential mechanistic insights.

Keywords: Cancer genes, graph neural Networks, heterophily, interpretability

1 Introduction

Identifying cancer genes is a critical step toward elucidating oncogenic mechanisms and therapeutic strategies. While comprehensive sequencing efforts, such as The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) and the International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC) [1, 2], have catalyzed the discovery of seminal genomic variants, many CGs remain unannotated. Rare, context-dependent, and pathway-embedded oncogenes frequently evade detection in existing repositories (e.g., COSMIC-CGC [3], NCG [4]), and the vast number of candidates further makes wet-lab experiments impractical. To bridge this gap, early attempts were rooted in positive selection on mutation frequency, detecting recurrently mutated genes by correcting for background rates [5, 6]. However, sensitive threshold risk inflates false positives or excludes low-frequency CGs. It has motivated a shift towards combining machine learning with biological knowledge. Representative methods such as DriverNet and OncoIMPACT [7, 8] incorporate biological priors into a supervised models, and DriverML further introduced a probabilistic framework to improve sensitivity to rare mutation patterns [9]. Despite progress, these methods are still challenged by established biological realities and non-isolated gene relationships. This facilitates advanced computational methods for analyzing complex structures.

As a typical method in graph representation learning, graph neural networks (GNNs) have attracted more interest in cancer genomics. They capture local structures of gene-encoded proteins by iterative message passing (MP) to identify cancer genes. In fact, recent graph-based methods, including EMOGI [10] and CGMega [11], combine protein-protein interaction graphs with multi-omics signals (e.g., gene expression and chromatin conformation) to balance topological context and biological evidence. Similar extensions that incorporate structural augmentation or multi-task learning further improve performance on CGs inference [12–14]. However, the shallow architecture of GNNs forces an oversimplification of gene interactions, which exceed immediate adjacencies, including dynamic signaling pathways, feedback loops, and co-regulators. For example, TP53 loss-of-function disrupts MYC inhibition and triggers oncogenic hyperactivation through intermediate effectors (e.g., MDM2, AKT) [15, 16]. While scaling up in depth could theoretically solve this limitation, its implementation is hampered by oversmoothing and parameter explosion. Additional convolutional layers lead to an exponential surge in parameter requirements and complicate the optimization. Some regularization strategies, such as DropEdge and DropNode [17, 18], partially alleviate, but inadvertently discard critical semantic information or truncate signaling pathways. Thus, topological distance challenges deciphering higher-order gene cooperation.

A further challenge is the heterophily of CG associations. Unlike homophilic social or citation networks, where nodes with similar features or labels cluster, the scarcity of CGs compels them to form connections with diverse genes rather than clustering (Supplementary S1). This implies that CGs with similar biological functions and semantic roles are not necessarily geographically close. For example, PIK3CA (a key oncogenic kinase) exhibits separation from its functionally homologous PTEN (phosphatase tumor suppressor), with only a small proportion of direct neighbors belonging to oncogenic pathways (e.g., AKT1) [19, 20]. Under such heterophily, standard message passing face inherent incompatibility: local aggregation may dilute CG signals with dominant non-cancer background, and recursive propagation can further amplifies

contaminated representations across scales (Supplementary S2). In addition, achieving endogenous interpretation remains an open challenge. Post-hoc explainers (e.g., GNNExplainer [21]) typically rely on external heuristics and may not faithfully reflect the model’s intrinsic decision process. In contrast, biological interpretability requires transparent architectures to trace polygenic regulatory relationships.

To address these challenges, we propose **CGMap**, a **M**ulti-scale **a**ware **p**ropagation framework for CG identification that shifts emphasis from depth stacking to a **width-oriented** learning paradigm. Instead of relying on layer-by-layer aggregation, CGMap employs One-shot Parallel Propagation (OPP) to construct hop-specific propagation channels based on shortest-path strata, enabling simultaneous access to neighborhood signals across multiple topological distances in a single forward pass. This design broadens the receptive field for spatially dispersed CGs while alleviating representation homogenization associated with deep stacking. To capture pathway-level cooperation, We further incorporate a pathway-centric diffusion process that quantify the strength of gene synergy beyond direct connectivity, yielding weighted virtual interactions that can be traced back to candidate regulatory routes for intrinsic interpretation. CGMap also adopts a lightweight parameterization by decoupling feature transformation from propagation, and integrates a generalized PageRank (GPR) fusion to balance local and global information adaptively.

Experimental results demonstrate that CGMap consistently outperforms all 12 baselines in both performance and computational efficiency. It exhibits superior robustness, stability, and resilience to oversmoothing. The fidelity and intrinsic interpretability further ensure the reliability of predictions. In addition, CGMap successfully reproduced known CGs from the COSMIC and OncoKB databases while orthogonal validation reveals six unannotated high-confidence candidates. We further provide the *in vitro* loss-of-function experiments that support pro-malignant roles of selected prioritized genes. To our knowledge, CGMap represents the first width-oriented GNN architecture for CGs identification, offering a shift in the flexibility and scalability of graph representation learning.

2 Results

2.1 Overall workflow of CGMap

CGMap offers a plug-and-play architecture, with modular components that can be independently replaced or extended. Its main objective is to identify CGs by integrating multi-omics data and multi-scale gene associations. Fig.1 presents the overall framework of CGMap and details in Methods. The workflow begins with extracting multi-omics features from 16 pan-cancer datasets, including mutation frequency, DNA methylation, differential expression, and ten global gene attributes such as gene essentiality and miRNA interactions. Following established data filtering and preprocessing [10, 13], these attributes are amalgamated using weighted contributions to construct a 58-dimensional gene feature matrix. Topological contexts are derived from three public biomolecular networks: protein-protein Interaction networks (PPI) from

STRING, pathway network integrating KEGG and Reactome, and GGNet comprising gene interactions from the Encyclopedia of RNA interactomes. These components collectively form the input to CGMap.

Fig. 1 Overview of the CGMap. **a**, Data collection and input graph construction. Four multi-omics features were integrated into a weighted matrix, where gene mutations were normalized by the average mutation rate. The resulting 58-dimensional matrix was respectively mapped on three different biomolecular networks to construct the input graph \mathcal{G} . **b**, Streamlined graph learning architecture. CGMap distills the traditional GNN paradigm into three sequential blocks: transformation layer, propagation layer, and multi-scale fusion layer. Components at each layer can be replaced with context-appropriate methods based on different tasks. The core propagation layer comprises OPP and a path diffusion block. The former employs a topological adjacency matrix measured by the shortest path to illustrate the K-order gene dependencies at different distances, while the latter incorporates all related paths between each gene pair to adjust their influence. Intuitively, they correspond to multi-scale neighborhood scope and fine-grained interaction relationships. All embeddings are balanced in the GPR fusion layer, and CGs are inferred based on their probabilities at the output layer. **c**, An intuitive comparison of traditional graph representation learning and ours. Supplementary S3 provides more details of the pipeline.

The basic backbone of CGMap is built on a separated GNN architecture, comprising two independent modules: feature transformation and propagation. During the feature encoding, a context-specific encoder $f_{\theta}(\cdot)$ generates gene representations agnostic to the structure, thereby ensuring feature purity. Here, we just instantiate $f_{\theta}(\cdot)$ as

a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) for simplicity. For topology pipeline, CGMap introduces one-shot parallel propagation (OPP), which focuses on capturing nodes with homophilic relationships distributed in different layers by disconnecting hierarchical dependencies in traditional MP. Theoretically, OPP encodes multi-scale neighbors via shortest-path distances, bypassing rigid graph propagation along the graph structure to overcome shallow-layer limitations, while ensuring each node is aggregated only once and avoiding redundant feature accumulation caused by depth-orientation (see Methods). Fig.1c and Fig.S3 further illustrates the difference between OPP and traditional MP, with Supplementary S3 detailing limitations of the latter. Inspired by evidence that interactions between disease-related genes may be more frequent [22], CGMap further accumulates synergistic interaction strengths for each gene pair across multiple pathways to simulate biological processes in disease contexts. The contribution of each pathway depends on the degree of all traversed nodes, which is aligned with the observation that hubs often exhibit higher connectivity within human disease networks [23]. Then, to balance multi-order samples, Generalized PageRank (GPR) factors adaptively weights the contributions of different scales. Recent work indicate that this adaptive method can learn polynomial graph filters tailored for low-frequency and high-frequency signals, thereby enabling flexible trade-offs between sample consistency and variability [24]. Final CGs predictions are output as risk scores through a logistic classifier.

2.2 CGMap boosts prediction performance and efficiency

Prediction performance. Our training dataset comprises high-confidence cancer genes (CGs) and non-CGs from public databases (796 positives vs. 2,187 negatives; Supplementary Data 1), with detailed statistics and a novel heterophily score (H.R) provided in Supplementary S4. H.R values approaching 1 indicate strong heterophily, whereas lower values reflect homophily.

To evaluate CGMap, baselines covering four categories: 1) classical GNNs (GCN [25], GAT [26], ChebNet [27], GATv2 [28]); 2) novel architectures (ARMAGNN [29], TAGCN [30], PMLP [31], AGNN [32]); 3) depth-oriented architecture (JKNet [33]); and 4) cancer-specific predictors (EMOGI [10], MTGCN [12], CGMega [11]). For fairness, each model evaluation undergoes 10 independent 5-fold cross-validation and reports the average results. Table 1 summarizes results under identical experimental settings, where the evaluation metrics relate to AUC (receiver operating characteristic curve), AUPR (class imbalance), and single-round training time.

Across all networks, CGMap consistently outperformed 12 baseline methods while maintaining low computational cost. On the GGNet (H.R = 0.943), which exhibits higher topological complexity among cancer genes, it exceeded the second-best method by 4.34% in AUC and 5.50% in AUPR. On the one hand, only approximately 6% to 7% of nodes in all networks are labeled as positive samples, creating a representative imbalanced scenario. On the other hand, as graph size and complexity of connections increase, the heterophilic level also rises (H.R: GGNet >PPI >PathNet). Under this dual influence, traditional baselines demonstrate performance degradation, whereas CGMap exhibits offsetting ability, particularly for stronger heterophily. This inversion

Table 1 Overall results on PPI, PathNet and GGNet in 5-CV test. Bold indicates the best performance and underlining indicates 2nd best

Method	PPI (H.R.=0.899)			PathNet (H.R.=0.876)			GGNet (H.R.=0.943)		
	AUC	AUPR	TIME*	AUC	AUPR	TIME*	AUC	AUPR	TIME*
GCN	80.10	72.08	0.0140	79.64	76.83	0.0059	61.17	50.46	0.0238
GAT	77.77	69.29	0.0192	74.95	71.71	0.0113	60.20	47.57	0.0342
GATv2	80.64	73.17	0.0495	78.86	73.42	0.0197	68.37	57.16	0.0994
ChebNet	81.14	75.62	0.0145	82.37	81.48	0.0098	78.28	71.50	0.0255
ARMAGNN	79.42	<u>78.98</u>	0.0103	79.98	82.12	0.0072	75.01	73.79	0.0172
TAGCN	82.58	<u>78.50</u>	0.0108	84.39	82.68	0.0079	<u>81.34</u>	<u>75.65</u>	0.0206
PMLP	65.80	47.86	0.0023	55.86	49.78	0.0023	57.44	45.97	0.0023
AGNN	80.61	72.56	0.0161	78.50	70.21	0.0082	70.35	58.82	0.0300
JKNet	81.22	75.15	0.0195	80.04	75.24	0.0108	64.84	55.85	0.0357
EMOGI	81.92	75.72	0.0150	82.48	81.64	0.0980	78.73	72.69	0.0258
MTGCN	<u>82.88</u>	78.75	0.9344	<u>84.43</u>	<u>82.86</u>	0.2980	81.18	73.70	2.0766
CGMega	<u>80.49</u>	76.16	0.0214	<u>80.23</u>	<u>78.51</u>	0.0157	78.29	71.63	0.0205
CGMap	87.07	83.95	<u>0.0065</u>	86.01	85.23	<u>0.0053</u>	85.68	81.15	<u>0.0057</u>

*Record the training time (s) for each epoch.

Fig. 2 Total training time and performance comparison of all 12 baselines reaching the best performance relative to CGMap on PPI, PathNet, and GGNet.

indicates that CGMap tends to leverage underlying gene associations as a basis for discrimination rather than overdependence on curated biochemical knowledge, which is often constrained by data purity requirements and rare oncogenic resources. Notably, these gains exceeded disease setting baselines. MTGCN achieves competitive results on PathNet by incorporating link prediction as an auxiliary task to recover partial connectivity. However, this advantage is confined to smaller networks, and the computational scalability will struggle with large biological networks. Other novel graph learning technologies, such as dynamic-attention models (GATv2), topology-adapted filters (TAGCN), and multi-hop residuals (JKNet), also outperformed classical GNNs, further validating that enhanced heterophilic association modeling improves CGs identification.

Prediction efficiency. Next, we evaluated the efficiency of CGMap on the benchmark datasets. Complementing Table 1, Fig.2 presents a scatter plot comparing the

total training time of all baselines to achieve their best performance relative to CGMap. For fairness, all methods were executed on the same NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU to eliminate timing bias from hardware differences. In synthesis, CGMap emerged as the strongest candidate, not only pulling away from the baselines in performance but also achieving substantial reductions in computational cost. Most baselines suffer from either lower accuracy or expensive training time. Compared to the recent prediction models such as EMOGI, CGMega and MTGCN, CGMap is even up to nearly ~ 1000 times faster on PPI. In addition, an interesting observation is that PMLP also achieves competitive training speed by deactivating its GNN block during training and calling it only during inference, effectively reducing training cost to approximately that of a standard MLP. While this two-stage design partially compensates for representation power by leveraging local neighborhood structure at test time, its limitations are evident under higher heterophily: PMLP exhibits a greater performance drop on GGNet than other methods. Therefore, even when simplifying GNN architectures, preserving their capacity to learn complex topological dependencies remains essential.

2.3 Ablation studies support the synergy of each component

To rigorously assess the functional contributions and biological relevance of each component in CGMap, we conducted an ablation study with four variants: 1) Sequential propagation: Replacing one-shot parallel propagation with traditional layer-wise MP; 2) Path-agnostic model: Removing Path-aware quantification between node pairs; 3) Static fusion: Eliminating GPR weights; 4) Separate GNN architecture only: Removing all components and retaining only fundamental transformation and propagation (MP) backbone.

As shown in Fig.3a, all variants exhibit varying degrees of performance degradation, confirming the necessity of collaborative work of each component. Among all networks, OPP outperforms sequential MP by 2.14%–4.48% in AUPR. By processing neighbor representations in parallel, it minimizes redundancy from repeated aggregation and multi-layer representation interference. After removing path attention, we found a catastrophic performance drop on PPI. From a biological perspective, OPP confers coarse-grained gene regulation over different topological distances, while pathway attention covers fine-grained associations triggered by key signaling cascades. Without pathway focus, all pathways are treated equally, ignoring the distinct signal processes corresponding to different pathways and reducing the biological context available for predictions. From a method perspective, parallel propagation interrupts the information flow of sequential propagation and instead assigns neighbors based on each gene pair’s shortest path (see Methods). This means that when genes have different lengths of regulatory relationships, they will only be assigned to the layer corresponding to their shortest path length. Therefore, excluding path attention will indirectly collapse the original topology structure with prior biological semantics into a less informative structure. More critically, all genes retained within the same layer will be considered to exert uniform influence. It contradicts reality, where genes with stronger interactions with CGs are more likely to constitute core cancer regulatory modules. Furthermore, PPIs typically form dense, small-world networks, where functionally important proteins frequently reside at the intersections of multiple signaling

Fig. 3 Comprehensive evaluation of CGMap. **a**, Comparison of CGMap components and analysis of their synergistic effects. **b**, Performance comparison of CGMap and representative SOTA baselines in resisting homogenization across layers 1–10. **c**, Track the evolution of GPR weights. **d**, Endogenous interpretability: The top 60 cancer regulatory pathways influencing prediction were reconstructed from CGMap. The left and right panels represent subgraphs formed by paths with $1 \leq L \leq 2$ and $2 \leq L \leq 4$, respectively. Highlighted and dashed lines respectively indicate homophilic patterns with greater predictive influence and established regulatory relationships. **e**, Enrichment of these pathways with $2 \leq L \leq 4$ in KEGG, REACTOME, and DisGeNET, confirming CGMap’s ability to track actual biological processes. **f**, The gene association modules of *MALT1* in the 1-6 hop subgraphs provided by CGMap.

pathways [34]. Removing pathway attention significantly reduces this cross-pathway identification ability. In contrast, the inherent pathways and gene interactions embedded in PathNet and GGNet networks are clearer, which explains why their relatively smaller performance declines.

It is worth noting that ablating GPR weights forces multi-layer representations to be fused by simple summation, which has a greater impact on higher heterophilic networks. This phenomenon reconfirms our two key points: 1) The utility of nearest

neighbors is limited in heterophilic contexts, where CGs tend to cluster with diverse partners; and 2) traditional low-pass GNN filters are insufficient for matching high-frequency signals triggered by local differences in such networks. As demonstrated in recent work [35], high-frequency signals induced by local differences can be jointly processed with low-frequency signals through an adaptive polynomial filter with signed coefficients. This also explains why ChebNet’s explicit polynomial design outperforms GCN and GAT under heterophilic conditions. Finally, even when only the separated backbone is retained, the variant performance is still superior to GCN, and the computational cost is lower, highlighting the negative impact of over-smoothing and the importance of parameter efficiency.

2.4 CGMap against homogenization

Depth robustness. As mentioned above, relying solely on proximal neighbor representations may be insufficient to distinguish CGs. A straightforward remedy is to expand the receptive field to cover distant CGs dependencies. However, the over-smoothing phenomenon confines existing GNNs to shallow architectures. To assess this influence, we gradually increased the number of layers in CGMap and several representative baselines under identical experimental conditions.

As expected, Fig.3b and Supplementary S5 reveal the unique resilience of CGMap: taking PPI as an example, its performance difference remains below $\pm 0.47\%$ across 1–10 layers, demonstrating an intrinsic resistance to feature homogeneity. In contrast, the baselines gradually decline beyond three layers. This divergence reflects that CGMap alleviates the inherent neighborhood “dilution” in sequential recursive aggregation. At a deeper level, repetitive node aggregation and averaging over consecutive neighbor information weaken the contrast between CGs and nonCGs representations, leading to a significant performance degradation of most baselines. Several baselines attempt to counteract oversmoothing, such as DropEdge (used in CGMega) for random edge removal. Similarly, JKNet uses residual-style jump connections to preserve deep information. MTGCN further combines both strategies to compensate for semantic distortion. However, CGMap obviates the need for any regularization strategy, preserving the integrity of the underlying network and avoiding redundant cross-layer noise. In fact, OPP allows for flexible representation combinations in a specific order without forcing layer stacking, but here we deliberately set the same 1-10 layers to examine the difference in CGMap.

GPR weights bring multiple layers of interpretability. Compared with GCN, the EMOGI curve based on polynomial filtering (Fig.3b) reinforces the interpretability of the above analysis. As a low-pass filter, GCN tends to preserve low-frequency information while filtering out high-frequency signals with local difference, which is insufficient for generalizing to heterophilic networks. CGMap also accounts for this scenario, where its adaptability stems from learnable GPR factors that dynamically reweight the contributions of different propagation layers. Most importantly, the weights alternate between positive and negative values across layers (Fig.3c), diverging from traditional schemes such as uniform weighting or exponential decay. On one hand, positive weights intuitively preserve important features in dominant layers and

resist representation convergence in deeper layers through subtraction. On the other hand, the learned weight distribution exhibits an adaptive transition from positive to negative dominance as depth increases. This polarity reversal aligns with the balancing mechanism proposed in recent spectral GNNs [36], where negative weights attenuate redundant low-frequency local similarities while amplifying discriminative high-frequency associative differences. Supplementary S6 confirm that constraining weights to equal values degrade performance by -2.84%, underscoring the necessity of signed weight learning.

2.5 Endogenous interpretability of path diffusion indicates key regulatory pathways in cancer pathogenesis

Deciphering the underlying gene regulatory mechanisms is extremely complex, and it involves extensive genomic sequencing and in vivo/ex vivo clinical experiments for co-screening. Fortunately, the topological interpretability of CGMap offers a possible solution to confirm and accelerate this process. More importantly, its endogenous pathway relationships implicitly provide decision support for predictions. To demonstrate this, we focused on established CGs and evaluated whether CGMap could recover experimentally validated pathways and prioritize novel interactions. Specifically, we reconstruct the virtual edges generated from OPP by tracking the original pathways and attention scores to identify the top 60 high-contribution pathways driving CGMap predictions. This approach also transforms discrete gene connections into quantifiable polygenic synergies. For clarity, Fig.3d presents the subgraph patterns of these 60 pathways, where gray lines depict several representative regulatory relationships (see Supplementary Data 17 for more pathways). Path lengths were restricted to $1 \leq L \leq 2$ and $2 \leq L \leq 4$ to balance objective realities: shorter paths may fail to encompass indirect regulation, while longer paths risk exceeding established biological knowledge and obscuring direct causality.

Overall, both subgraphs capture the homophilic patterns where cancer CGs are directly interconnected, and the prevalence of these prediction-beneficial homophilic associations increases at larger path length L . This aligns with our expectation that CGMap can effectively mark homophilic patterns embedded within heterophilic networks as critical pathways influencing prediction. While the inherent heterophily of shorter paths reduces the availability of direct CG interactions, these prioritized regulatory patterns remain consistent with existing evidence. For example, multiple *CASP8*-mediated pathways were reconstructed, reinforcing its pivotal role in extrinsic apoptosis and emerging non-apoptotic tumor microenvironment modulation. The death-inducing signaling complex (DISC) was accurately recapitulated, where *FADD* links *CASP8* to *TNFSF10* (*TRAIL*) and facilitates regulated activation of apoptotic cascades. It is consistent with *CASP8*'s tumor-suppressive functions in colorectal and breast cancers [37–39]. Path 25 (**CASP8-BCL2L1-CASP2**) reveals a novel regulatory mechanism: *CASP8* not only initiates apoptosis but also modulates survival signals via the anti-apoptotic protein *BCL2L1* (*BCL-XL*), which is frequently overexpressed in therapy-resistant tumors. This dual role aligns with recent studies on ovarian cancer, where *CASP8* balances apoptosis and survival pathways to promote tumor progression and treatment resistance [40, 41]. Beyond apoptosis, CGMap

reproduced Path 4 (**SIX1-EYA1-DACH1**), the retinal determination gene network (RDGN), a critical developmental pathway in cancer. *SIX1* is a well-established driver of metastasis in triple-negative breast cancer and regulates transcription by interacting with *EYA1*. The result suggests that the *SIX1-EYA1* complex may affect *DACH1*, a known Wnt/ β -catenin antagonist. Although *DACH1* is considered a tumor suppressor, emerging evidence indicates that its function depends highly on the environment. [42–45]. For example, abnormal co-expression of *SIX1/EYA* and *DACH1* disrupts the physiological balance, promoting ductal hyperplasia and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), which further progresses to ductal carcinoma. Such EMT events are widely believed to endow subsets of malignant cells with cancer stem cell properties, facilitating basement membrane to enter blood vessels, thereby triggering metastasis. Consistent with recent reports on RNA editing-driven mutagenesis, several reconstructed paths also implicate the *APOBEC* family [46–49], particularly *APOBEC3B* of kataegis clusters in breast and lung cancers, supporting the role of *APOBEC* enzymes as contributors to cancer mutation signatures [50–52]. Another key advance of CGMap is its ability to infer richer regulatory details in longer pathways ($2 \leq L \leq 4$), overcoming previous limitations in capturing higher-order correlations. For example, Path 5 (**CASP8-FAS-STAT5B-BCL2L1-CFLAR**) extends the apoptosis and survival balance: *FAS-CASP8* signaling initiates apoptosis [53, 54] and *STAT5B* upregulates anti-apoptotic *BCL2L1* [55], while *CFLAR* directly inhibits *CASP8* to form a regulatory circuit for ovarian cancer chemotherapy resistance [56]. Notably, both subgraphs also implicate circadian clock disruption in tumorigenesis (**PER1-CRY1-ARNTL-CRY2-PER3**). The *PER/CRY* complex regulates DNA repair genes, and its dysregulation has been linked to genomic instability in hepatocellular carcinoma [57, 58]. Finally, CGMap prioritizes hallmark CGs (e.g., TP53, STAT5B, and TRAF2) as central hubs in top pathways, consistent with their dominant roles across multiple cancers.

We further performed enrichment analysis of these pathways in KEGG, Reactome, and DisGeNet. As shown in Figure 3e and Supplementary S7, these pathways exhibit an intuitive association with cancer, particularly for higher-order pathways. It highlights that capturing long-range gene dependencies improves the biological plausibility of predictions. In addition, it also supports the transparency of CGMap in CGs identification. Without requiring external heuristics for post hoc interpretation, this interpretability stems from fine-grained regulatory attention. These findings collectively elucidate the rationale behind the CGMap decision-making process.

2.6 Virtual edge weights decode multi-scale gene interactions and novel targets

OPP and path awareness mechanism convert genes with arbitrary positional associations into quantified virtual direct-edge weights, thereby accumulating more implicit multi-order dependencies and biological topology semantics. It prompts us to consider whether this mechanism could facilitate the exploration of novel gene associations, even if they may not be directly connected in a heterophilic setting, thereby aiding in the analysis of potential target design. Therefore, unlike pathway reshaping in the above section, we directly examine the dependency scores between nodes.

As illustrated in Fig.3f, we mapped the significant gene associations across hops 1–6, using the key cancer gene *MALT1* in lymphoma and autoimmune diseases as a case study. At proximal hops, CGMap located common oncogenic partners of *MALT1* with high ranking. These interaction are dominated by established components of antigen receptor and death receptor signalling, including *CASP8*, *CARD11*, *BCL10*, *IKBKB* and *TLR4*, which consistent with *MALT1*'s central role in CBM complex assembly, NF- κ B activation and innate immunity [59–62]. In tumor immune evasion, *MALT1* bridges *BCL10* via its death domain and participates the *CARD11–BCL10–MALT1* (CBM) complex [59, 63], activating NF- κ B signaling. This drives tumor cell secretion of *CSF1*, *PGE2*, and *CXCL1*, which promote M2-type macrophage polarization and reinforce an immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment [64, 65]. Recent work further corroborates this finding [66], using antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs) targeting both the protease activity and death domain of *MALT1* effectively inhibit tumor growth in patient tumor samples and preclinical mouse models. Furthermore, CGMap also revealed understudied factors, such as *CHUK* and *CARD10*, potentially bridging *MALT1*-paracaspase activity to IKK complex activation and *CARMA* family redundancy [67–69]. Despite limited evidence, *CHUK* serves as the catalytic subunit of the IKK complex, with its kinase activity regulated by CBM complex-mediated signaling [70, 71].

Beyond local interactions, the heatmap also exposes higher scores but distant associations. Although the weight decays after 3 hops, some genes still retain large weights. It indicated that multi-hop influence is selective, not uniform, which supports that CGMap discriminates meaningful long-range dependencies. At 4–6 hops, the top associations shift toward extracellular matrix (ECM) and stromal modulators (multiple *COL* family members, *COL1A1/COL2A1/COL6A3*, *LUM*). Although these genes are not immediate interactors of *MALT1* in the PPI, their high scores suggest that *MALT1*-centred signalling can propagate through intermediate cascades to influence tumour–stroma interactions and microenvironmental remodelling. *MALT1* activity in tumour cells and immune compartments can modulate cytokine and chemokine release that, in turn, affect fibroblast and ECM dynamics [72]. Literature evidence also confirms that tumor metastasis and ECM remodeling are multifaceted and synergistic processes [73, 74].

As expected, these observations reveal two practical values of CGMap. Methodologically, OPP plus path-awareness translates arbitrary positional relationships into quantitative studies, whether examining local or global interaction possibilities. Practically, the high-scoring partners provide novel hypotheses: for example, perturbation of *MALT1* should alter expression or activity of the predicted ECM components if the inferred multi-step regulatory routes are operative. Therefore, these candidates (e.g. *COL* genes) may represent prioritized targets for subsequent investigation, either targeted perturbation in relevant lymphoma models or interrogation in bulk and single-cell tumour datasets to seek concordant transcriptional and microenvironmental signatures.

Fig. 4 CGMap’s confidence in prediction. **a**, Reliability analysis. Quantitative study of the true prediction composition from CGMap and established baselines. **b**, Fidelity analysis. Comparison of the original (left panel) and predicted gene embeddings (right panel) in the TSNE visualization results, where the different colors in the left encode the true gene classes from expert knowledge, and the right colors corresponding to the predicted gene classes. **c**, Data scarcity scenario analysis. Performance comparison of CGMap and other methods under different proportions of training samples. **d**, Stability analysis. For CGMap, 10%-50% of interactions are randomly removed via a Bernoulli binomial mask. Scatter points and upper/lower bounds indicate the model’s error intervals. **e**, Venn diagram showing 70 overlapping high-confidence predictions from the intersection of the top 150 genes in all datasets.

2.7 CGMap enhances cancer gene screening ability

A key application of CGMap is screening cancer genes, which are difficult to compile manually due to their complexity. We focus on comparing CGMap with methods designed for CG prediction and selecting GCN, EMOGI, CGMega, and MTGCN as representative baselines. Supplementary data 2-16 present the gene rankings produced

by each model across different networks, where each gene is assigned a predicted probability and CG label with a threshold of 0.5.

Our predictions demonstrate that CGMap accurately identifies established CGs and ranks highly prevalent genes such as *TP53*, *PIK3CA*, *BRAF*, and *APC* at the top. In contrast, competing baselines yield partial omissions (e.g., *BRAF* #1 CGMap) or lowering the rankings such as *PTEN* (#6 CGMap, #665 CGMega, #2158 GCN), *PIK3CA* (#8 CGMap, #509 EMOGI), and *AR* (#186 CGMap, #722 MTGCN, #837 EMOGI, #1604 CGMega), many of which are widely recognized as critical cancer genes in clinical practice. Notably, CGMap uniquely upgrades higher ranks to genes such as *NOTCH3*, *CASP8*, and *ASH1L*, which are ranked below #2000 or even #4000 in other baselines. Recent reports confirm the relevance of these genes across multiple cancers, including breast cancer, lung cancer, bladder cancer, and pituitary tumors [75]. In head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC), *NOTCH3* is increasingly recognized as a known driver of metastasis, and its inhibition improves mouse survival [76, 77]. Similarly, *EPHB4* is a key tumor suppressor in intestinal tumors and holds potential as a therapeutic target for colorectal cancer [78], but it ranks significantly lower in competitive methods. In addition, several baselines, such as EMOGI, tend to conservatively label an overabundance proportion of predictions as CGs conservatively, even though they may not be genuine oncogenic factors. It motivated us to consider whether the predictions are reliable and what scale should be used to measure the quality of predictions, as the universally accepted gold standard does not exist.

2.8 CGMap enhances prediction reliability and fidelity

Since the number of CGs in real cancers is not fully known, discovering a sufficient number of CGs is critical. However, too many predictions will result in a lack of confidence, and too few may overlook key genes. Therefore, we performed a condensed analysis to explore CGMap predictions from a reliability perspective. Specifically, we used a set of high-confidence candidate CGs (CCGs; Supplementary data 1) from the NCG 7.2 database to complement the real-world known CGs (KCGs). We divide all predicted CGs into KCGs, CCGs, nonCGs (NCGs), and potential CGs (PCGs, not yet determined) to explore the real composition of the model predictions.

As illustrated in Fig.4a, CGMap achieves a higher proportion of KCGs and CCGs under a consistent threshold and exhibits a lower misclassification rate for NCG. This leading advantage is more pronounced on the GGNet with higher heterophily, aligning with the results in Table 1. Although deeper or residual architectures capture additional CGs, their increased NCGs still diminish discriminative power. In this context, CGMap benefits from its unique “customized” aggregation mechanism and insights from local to global. In addition, we further assessed model fidelity by visualizing the learned gene representations with t-distributed stochastic neighborhood embedding (t-SNE), where matching color codes for the ground truth and model predictions (Fig.4b and Supplementary S8). The ground truth visualization reflects the original cancer and other gene distribution. The results reveal three key insights: 1) CGMap’s embedding exhibits tighter spatial alignment with the ground truth, which demonstrates the

Fig. 5 Validation results of oncogenes predicted by CGMap. **a**, Gene class breakdown. Doughnut chart showing the composition percentage of 70 cancer genes predicted by CGMap. Insets list representative genes in each class. **b**, GO enrichment analysis. Horizontal bar plot of the top 20 Gene Ontology terms ranked by $-\log_{10}(p\text{-value})$, and colored by significance. **c**, KEGG pathway enrichment. Bubble chart of enriched cancer and related signaling pathways, where bubble size denotes gene count and color indicates false discovery rate (FDR); pathways in cancer top the list. **d**, DisGeNET disease association. Radial bar (circular) plot of the most significantly associated diseases from DisGeNET, with bar length proportional to enrichment score; blue bars indicate high relevance to malignant neoplasms. **e**, Hallmark cancer process chord diagram. Chord connecting each gene to the 10 “Hallmarks of Cancer” demonstrates CGMap’s recovery of core oncogenic processes. **f**, WikiPathways interaction diagram. Enriched pathways are displayed as the top 20 strongest terms.

model’s ability to isolate oncogenic signals from complex data. In contrast, most base-lines yield incomplete and fragmented reconstructions; 2) CGMap selectively amplifies substructures, especially for regions with dense non-CGs; 3) It provides novel candidate factors beyond known databases (COSMIC, OncoKB, etc.). Most of them showed enrichment in cancer signature pathways (See Fig.5b, c: $p < 1e - 5$ for “Pathways in cancer” and “MAPK Cascade”). Importantly, the predicted number (1700–2500)

closely matches the magnitude of missing cancer genes reported in comprehensive resources such as the Network of Cancer Genes [3] and pan-cancer analyses [79–81]. These evidence support confidence in CGMap and the potential prediction value.

2.9 CGmap enhances stability under data constraints

To demonstrate the robustness of CGMap under different data scenarios, we constructed multi-ratio small sample evaluation and interaction perturbation evaluation. For the former, we randomly select 10% to 90% of positive samples and an equal proportion of negative samples from the original data as the training set (keeping the original data class distribution). As shown in Fig.4c and Supplementary S9, CGMap consistently leads at every sampling rate. Even only 10% of the data for training, it achieves a peak performance of 78.26%, with performance stabilizing as more samples are added.

For the latter, we progressively modified the original network using a binary Bernoulli mask to assess its robustness under interaction perturbations ranging from 10% to 50% (Fig.4d; Supplementary S10). As the structure gradually deteriorates, CGMap exhibits a slight, but expected decline in performance. The injected noise inevitably degrades model accuracy. However, the minimal fluctuations observed confirm the robustness of CGMap, which benefits from the global neighborhood information compensating for the missing edges.

2.10 Enhanced prediction outlook and confidence

Given the incomplete understanding of cancer mechanisms and the evolving expert annotations, any prediction method carries inherent uncertainty. To mitigate this effect, we intersected the top 150 genes from three sources (PPI, PathNet, and GGNet) and yielded 70 overlapping high-confidence predictions. The corresponding venn diagram and the proportions of candidates are shown in Fig.4e and Fig.5a. The complete gene annotations are listed in Supplementary S11. Next, we profile these high-scoring candidate genes through enrichment analysis using Gene Ontology (GO), Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG), and DisGeNET/WikiPathways databases, revealing their roles in biological processes, signaling cascades, and disease associations. The 20 most significant terms are depicted in Fig.5b, c, d, where bar lengths are proportional to $-\log_{10}(p\text{-value})$, indicating the statistical significance of the associated causal groups. Fig.5f clusters nodes by term similarity, encoding enrichment degree and term identity via size and color.

We noticed these genes are involved in regulating transcriptional activity, particularly in gene expression regulation, transcriptional positive regulation, and DNA-template, which are essential for oncogenic reprogramming. The MAPK cascade and phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K) signaling axis are frequently dysregulated in cancer, and their enrichment supports that these genes may contribute to aberrant oncogenic signaling. Another intuitive evidence is that terms related to high-incidence diseases such as malignant neoplasms, cancer pathway, and specific malignancies (e.g., colorectal cancer, breast cancer, head and neck cancer, and prostate cancer) are over-represented across KEGG, DisGeNet and WikiPathways. Similarly, pathways like

FoxO signaling, central carbon metabolism in cancer, and non-small cell lung cancer also emphasize roles in tumor metabolisms, survival, and progression. It has been reported that changes in central carbon metabolism will promote the rapid proliferation of cancer cells [82, 83]. In addition, associations with breast adenocarcinoma, gastric adenocarcinoma, and endometrial carcinoma may help elucidate their relevance to specific cancer subtypes. Interestingly, intellectual disability emerged as an unexpected but notable association. This suggests that they may have potential pleiotropic effects beyond cancer, as demonstrated by BRCA1 in the hippocampus maintaining neuronal genome integrity and normal learning and memory functions [84, 85]. However, these genes were either not predicted or ranked with low confidence in previous methods. Finally, our gene set maps onto all ten hallmarks of cancer (e.g., sustained proliferation, invasion/metastasis, replicative immortality; Fig.5e), with each hallmark criterion supported by ≥ 18 predicted genes ($p < 0.05$). These criteria were initially defined by Hanahan and Weinberg to reveal biological capabilities acquired during tumor development [86].

2.11 Discovery of novel candidates

Exploring potential candidates that could actually be CGs is crucial for therapeutic interventions. Therefore, this section highlights novel predictions from the high-confidence set (Fig.5a) that absent from the curated cancer gene catalogs. By excluding established KCGs and CCGs, we identify six genes, including *FN1*, *TTN*, *RYR2*, *RYR3*, *PCLO*, and *LRP2*, which lack consensus in current annotations. In this study, they are prioritized as oncogenic candidates.

Expression patterns in various tumors. To evaluate the potential oncogenic roles of these previously overlooked candidate genes, we analyzed their expression patterns across multiple cancer transcriptomic databases. Taking *FN1* as an example, the box plot in Fig.6a shows the gene expression differences in all TCGA cancers, where only the tumor group is shown for cancers lacking normal controls. Compared with the normal group, *FN1* was significantly upregulated in various cancer types, including glioblastoma (GBM), breast cancer (BRCA), and bladder cancer (BLCA) ($p < 0.001$, Wilcoxon test). The Kaplan–Meier survival curves derived from GEPIA2 data [87] further validated the potential association between abnormal *FN1* expression and overall survival (Fig.6b; Fig.S11). Patients in the high-expression group (e.g., GBM, HR = 1.5, $p = 0.023$) generally had poorer overall survival, suggesting that *FN1* may be associated with poor prognosis. To validate these findings, we further examined the real spatial transcriptomic sequencing data from the CROST database [88]. We observed that the *FN1* signal distribution was significantly expressed in multiple tumor sections and was higher than that in adjacent normal tissues (Fig.6c). This supports its potential functional relevance to cancer.

Immune infiltration level. To assess the impact of these novel candidates on tumor microenvironment, we quantified the immune infiltration levels in the TIMR3 database (containing 15 deconvolution algorithms and 33 cancer types from TCGA) [89]. Fig.6d shows the expression correlation with CD8⁺ T cells, macrophages, and CAFs using *FN1* as an example ($p < 0.05$, purity adjusted), where the spearman

Fig. 6 Multiple evidences support CGMap-predicted novel candidates. **a**, Panoramic view of *FN1* expression differences across different tumor types in the TCGA database ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$; $***p < 0.001$). **b**, Kaplan-Meier curves showing *FN1* gene expression levels in example cancers, illustrating its association with survival prognosis (95% confidence intervals are shown as dashed lines). HR was calculated on the basis of the Cox proportional hazards model, taking the high expression group as the intervention group [HR (high)]. **c**, Visualization of *FN1* gene expression hotspots in tumor tissues section via spatial transcriptomic database mapping. **d**, Immune infiltration analysis (CD8⁺ T, macrophages, and CAFs) reveals the association between the *FN1* gene and the immune microenvironment. **e**, Single-cell functional heatmap of *FN1* in pan-cancer.

coefficient assess these genes. Given the biochemical properties of *FN1*, we focused below on three cell types that have a mechanistic link to fibronectin. We found that *FN1* expression in most tumors is consistently negatively correlated with CD8⁺ T cells, consistent with our expectations and providing evidence of an immunosuppressive environment. Intuitively, *FN1* inhibits the infiltration of cytotoxic T cells, thereby obstructing extracellular matrix immune surveillance and allowing cancer cells to evade

immune killing. Conversely, *FN1* shows a significant positive correlation with CAF and macrophage infiltration levels, particularly M2 macrophages. Recent studies indicate that *FN1*, as a ligand for macrophage integrin ($\alpha_5\beta_1$), triggers two carcinogenic pathways: inducing macrophage polarization toward the M2 type (secreting IL-10 and TGF- β 1 to suppress immunity) and promoting macrophage secretion of MMP-9 (degrading the matrix to facilitate cancer cell metastasis) [90, 91]. Additionally, as a major secreted factor and activator of CAFs, *FN1* potentially further drives tumor growth [92]. This synergistic effect between the loss of immune function and the acquisition of stromal immunosuppressive components mechanistically explains why *FN1* may qualify as a candidate for a cancer gene.

Single-cell biochemical function. Finally, we validated the biological functions of these genes in the tumor microenvironment using the CancerSEA database (involving 14 functional states of 41,900 cancer single cells across 25 cancer types) [93]. The results indicate that these candidates are closely associated with multiple malignant tumors (Fig. 6e and Fig. S13). Taking *FN1* as an example, the dataset most significantly associated with EMT signaling (≥ 10) is shown in the figure, and this association trend exhibits a strong positive correlation across various solid tumors, including LUAD, BRCA, GBM, and CRC. Both invasion and metastasis functions also exhibit consistent positive correlation trends, suggesting that *FN1* upregulation may influence the potential evolution of cancer. The remaining candidate genes in Supplementary S12 are also associated with functional enrichment related to most malignant tumors, with a concentration in apoptosis, differentiation, DNA damage, and DNA repair. These findings further reinforce the potential value of these genes and provide support for CGMap.

2.12 Experimental validation in cancer cell lines

While the above analyses provide relevant evidence from external resources, more direct validation is required to substantiate the prediction of CGMap. To this end, we selected two top-ranked representative genes, *FN1* and *TTN*, for in vitro loss-of-function validation across multiple cancer cell contexts. This provides more rigorous evidence for CGMap’s ability to discover candidates beyond known oncogenes. Specifically, small interfering RNA (siRNA)-mediated knockdown experiments were performed in three representative human cancer cell lines: U251 (glioblastoma, GBM), A549 (lung adenocarcinoma, LUAD), and MDA-MB-231 (triple-negative breast cancer, TNBC). The impact on core malignant phenotypes—proliferation, migration, invasion, and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) was quantified using CCK-8, wound healing, Transwell, and Western blot analyses, respectively (detailed protocols are provided in Supplementary S13). The results are illustrated in Fig. 7.

Silencing *FN1* or *TTN* inhibits cancer cell proliferation. First, the knockdown efficiency of *FN1* and *TTN* was verified by WB, and the siRNA with the best efficiency was selected accordingly (Fig. S14). Then, we assessed the effect on cell viability using CCK-8 assays. Compared with the negative control group (si-NC), knockdown of *FN1* (si-*FN1*) or *TTN* (si-*TTN*) significantly inhibited the proliferation

Fig. 7 Experimental validation of the oncogenic roles of CGMap-predicted targets *FN1* and *TTN*. **a**, Cell proliferation was assessed using CCK-8 assays in A549, MDA-MB-231, and U251 cells transfected with negative control siRNA (si-NC), si-*FN1*, or si-*TTN* at 0, 24, 48, and 72 hours. **b**, Representative immunofluorescence images of Ki67 staining (green) indicating proliferative activity. Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI (blue). Scale bars, 20 μ m. **c**, Assessment of cell migration via wound healing assays. Representative images show scratch closure at 0, 12, 24, and 48 hours (left), with quantitative analysis of the migration area (right). **d**, Evaluation of cell invasion using Transwell assays. Representative images of crystal violet-stained invaded cells are shown (top), followed by the quantification of invasion cell numbers (bottom). **e**, Western blot analysis showing the protein expression levels of E-cadherin, N-cadherin, and Vimentin following *FN1* or *TTN* knockdown. GAPDH served as the loading control. Data are presented as mean \pm S.D. of three independent experiments. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ versus the si-NC group (Student's t-test).

of all three cell lines over a 72-hour period (Fig. 7a). Immunofluorescence staining results further corroborated this finding, where the well-established proliferation marker Ki67 was significantly reduced following *FN1* or *TTN* silencing (Fig. 7b). This indicates a reduced proliferative activity in the knockdown group.

***FN1* and *TTN* knockdown reverses the EMT phenotype.** Given that *FN1* and *TTN* may be associated with EMT and metastasis, we next investigated the functional impact on cell motility. Wound healing assays revealed that the migratory potential of cancer cells was significantly impaired in the si-*FN1* and si-*TTN* groups (Fig. 7c). More conclusively, Transwell invasion assays demonstrated a substantial decrease in the number of cells capable of penetrating a Matrigel-coated membrane following knockdown, affirming that these genes are critical for sustaining the invasive phenotype of these cancers (Fig. 7d). To elucidate the molecular mechanism underlying the observed changes in migration and invasion, we analyzed the expression of key EMT markers. The results showed that silencing *FN1* or *TTN* consistently led to an upregulation of the epithelial adhesion molecule E-cadherin, coupled with a downregulation of the mesenchymal markers N-cadherin and Vimentin across all three cell lines (Fig. 7e). This molecular shift indicates a partial reversion from a mesenchymal, invasive state toward a more epithelial, sedentary state, providing a potential mechanistic link between these genes and the metastatic of cancer cells.

In summary, these experimental results validate the biological significance of the candidates prioritized by the CGMap. More importantly, these findings complement the large-scale database analysis, collectively indicating that these genes play a critical role in sustaining core oncogenic phenotypes.

3 Dissussion and Conclusion

Deciphering latent cancer genes is critical for clinical intervention and therapeutic development. However, tumorigenesis is not solely from isolated mutations but from accumulation of genomic alterations and regulatory effects. In this context, we realized several interconnected challenges: 1) **Topological heterophily from cancer gene scarcity.** The scarcity of CGs causes them to disperse across different regions of the network rather than forming dense local clusters on a single scale, which not only generates heterophilic interactions that contradict the homophily assumption in graph representation learning but also hinders their localization; 2) **Restricted global dependencies.** Although a global perspective can alleviate spatial dispersion, traditional deep structures cause rapid representation convergence and cover more non-CGs. Layer-wise information flow in turn contaminates gene representations across depths and introduces redundancy by repeated aggregation at single nodes; 3) **Overlooked Polygenic synergistic cooperation.** Expert knowledge alone cannot fully describe the multiscale regulatory relationships, and traditional graph learning methods limit node neighborhoods to uniform, fixed distances. It contradicts empirical observations and underestimates functional associations among dispersed CGs; 4) **the demand for transparent interpretability.** The underlying network semantics underpin the model’s predictions, yet existing heuristic interpretation strategies struggle to provide intuitive interpretations of the model.

To improve CG identification and explore potential possibilities, we developed CGMap, a graph representation learning driven by a width perspective and path awareness. CGMap can be regarded as a generalized framework to cope with heterophilic gene networks and fine-grained gene dependencies flexibly. By eliminating

homophily-driven inductive biases, CGMap consistently outperforms 12 baselines in heterophilic environments, and prevents amplification and dilution of cancer-specific signals due to local neighborhood homogenization. In addition, the streamlined backbone of CGMap achieves computational efficiency up to three orders of magnitude on PPI, demonstrating its practicality and providing inspiration for larger molecular networks. Reliability studies confirm that CGMap prediction compositions exhibit higher consistency with expectations, and graph recovery tests further indicate they are closer to the original graph distribution state, both of which deepen the credibility of CGMap predictions. Although definitive validation of cancer genes remains limited by the lack of an established gold standard, enrichment analysis and literature evidence tie CGMap predictions to malignant tumor pathways. More importantly, leveraging parallel propagation, CGMap enhances the stability and robustness by incorporating multi-hop information. Even in large data offsets, noisy or incomplete perturbation interaction sets, it still maintains a high level of effectiveness. Meanwhile, hierarchical message passing governed by shortest-path metrics, ensuring nodes do not experience redundant aggregation since each neighbor is aggregated only once.

Another advancement of CGMap lies in its intrinsic interpretability, which comes from two key insights: a coarse-grained hierarchical propagation guidance factor (GPR) and node interactions with global pathway awareness. The former directly infers distance dependencies between gene nodes across multiple parallel channels, and the latter is supported by expert knowledge underlying the network, which fine-grains quantifies pathway associations into the strength of interactions for each pair of node virtualizations. By re-tracking the regulation with higher contribution, CGMap provides interpretability for prediction from the comprehensive perspective of multi-gene cooperation and different distance dependencies. The results are not limited to cancer but include additional disease contexts, such as circadian rhythms and brain disorders, which largely match existing reports on pleiotropic regulation. When we directly examine interaction partners with higher attention scores, CGMap points to known and potential gene interactions, especially with more distant high-score partners. It may accelerate target screening or drug design.

After combining high-confidence predictions shared by all networks, we recommend 70 cancer genes, including 40 known, 23 candidates, and 6 novel oncogenic candidates lacking consensus. This highlights the potential of CGMap to extend the cancer gene catalog. More encouragingly, our findings is further supported by real functional validation, multiplatform analyses and relevant literatures, where representative genes demonstrate oncogenic phenotypes in cell proliferation, migration, invasion, and EMT-related molecular assays. In addition, inference of gene dependencies and the understudied pathways proposed by CGMap still require additional validation to elucidate whether their roles are as expected. Therefore, the niche of CGMap still tends to accelerate and complement in-domain analysis and research. In the future, we will explore the integration of temporal dynamics into CGMap to enable precise genetic prediction at cancer-specific stages and focus on how to construct universal cancer gene measures in the face of constrained clinical practice.

4 Methods

4.1 Data source

In this study, we combined currently established pioneering processing methods to extract mutation [10], DNA methylation, and gene expression data from 29,446 samples encompassing 16 cancer types from TCGA. Each omics data was processed separately through the data workflow corresponding to EMOGI and then combined with gene system-level properties from curated database annotations in sysSVM [94]. This results in a complete gene feature matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 58}$, where each gene is assigned a 58-dimensional feature vector \mathbf{x}_i . The three heterophilic biomolecular networks were derived from [13]: 1) the String database [95]; 2) a network of KEGG, Reactome pathways, and interconnected biochemical pathways in cells and organisms [96]; and 3) a gene-interaction network formed from RNA-interaction data [97]. Detailed statistics for each dataset are provided in Supplementary S4, containing gene node numbers, edge numbers, positive and negative sample sizes, network average degree, Edge density, and a metric we propose for the degree of heterophily, H.R*.

Here, samples labeled as positive usually refer to genes that are positively associated with cancer, and the opposite refers to negative samples. These positive genes were compiled primarily through a collection of high-confidence samples compiled from established cancer gene databases NCG, COSMIC CGC, and PubMed abstracts after DigSEE [98] searches. Negative samples were mainly excluded on a case-by-case basis for genes that may be associated with cancer based on currently common evidence standards [10]. More details are shown in Supplementary data 1.

4.2 Architecture of CGMap

Streamlined graph representation learning pipeline. A core limitation of vanilla GNNs is the tight coupling of feature transformation (T) and propagation (P) within each layer. In practice, this coupling inflates parameter counts and exacerbates oversmoothing with increasing depth. For example, the standard two-layer GCN formulation is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \text{softmax} \left(\hat{\mathbf{A}} \sigma \left(\hat{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{W}^{(0)} \right) \mathbf{W}^{(1)} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{W}^{(*)}$ corresponds to the trainable weight matrices. $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the nonlinear activation function (e.g., ReLU). Stacking additional GCN layers will continuously introduce new transform-propagate blocks, rapidly expanding learnable parameters and deepening activation sequences. Critically, repeated ReLU operations accelerate node representation smoothing, degrading discriminative power in deep architectures [99]. To maintain a clearer learning space, CGMap separates transformation from propagation, confining complexity to the initial step. In the transformation phase, raw features are projected through a folded learnable function:

$$\mathbf{H}^0 = f_{\theta}(\mathbf{X}) \quad (2)$$

where $f_\theta(\cdot)$ is the feature transformation function. Actually, there are many options for $f_\theta(\cdot)$, such as Transformer, Autoencoder, or even a combination of CNN and specific encoders under more different types of multimodal data (Hic, temporal information, etc.). Here, we only use a simple MLP to contrast with traditional GNN. Subsequently, the propagation phase eliminates the need for further nonlinearities, utilizing node high-order neighbor information at a lower computational cost:

$$\mathbf{H}^k = \mathbf{P}^{(k)} \mathbf{H}^{k-1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{P} denotes the propagation matrix, which is typically specified as the normalized adjacency matrix $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ in existing GNNs that inherit the Message Passing mechanism. However, as mentioned above, stacking layers means being subject to more heterophilic close neighbor interactions, repeated node smoothing, and inter-layer interference caused by recursive sequence flow. More importantly, each gene equally affects its surrounding neighbors, whether homophily or heterophily. To this end, CGMap proposes the OPP block for multi-scale interaction extraction and a pathway-aware mechanism blocks to quantify gene cooperativity.

One-shot parallel propagation (OPP). OPP is built on three rules: 1) breaking the deep view shift to width expansion to capture interactions at more distant nodes; 2) width-first neighborhood search ensures that nodes are aggregated only once, and 3) A parallel channel to isolate multi-hop representation interference. Given the gene node v_u , we redefine the finer topological matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_u^{(k)} &= \left\{ v \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \bigcup_{m=0}^{k-1} \mathcal{L}_u^{(m)} \mid \exists w \in \mathcal{L}_u^{(k-1)}, (w, v) \in \mathcal{E} \right\}, \\ \mathbf{B}_{uv}^{(k)} &= \begin{cases} 1, & v \in \mathcal{L}_u^{(k)} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq K \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_u^{(k)}$ contains neighbor nodes reachable by the shortest path length k from v_u , and $\mathcal{L}_u^{(0)}$ is v_u . Therefore, this hierarchical definition of BFS yields a set of local to global transfer matrices $[\mathbf{B}^{(1)}, \mathbf{B}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{B}^{(K)}]$. Each entity $\mathbf{B}^{(k)}$ portrays the relationship between nodes separated by only k distances away from each other. The normalized propagation operator for each layer can be formalized as:

$$\mathbf{S}^{(k)} = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{D}}^{(k)} \right)^{-1/2} \left(\mathbf{B}^{(k)} + \mathbf{I} \cdot \delta_{k,1} \right) \left(\tilde{\mathbf{D}}^{(k)} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}^{(k)} = \text{diag} \left(\sum_j (\mathbf{B}^{(k)} + \mathbf{I} \cdot \delta_{k,1})_{ij} \right)$ is degree matrix corresponding to $\mathbf{B}^{(k)}$. $\delta_{k,1}$ is the Kronecker delta function that only instructs the addition of self-loops at $k = 1$. $\{\mathbf{S}^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^K$ strictly separates the interactions along the sequential flow at different topological distances. From the perspective of over-smoothing, each channel of OPP corresponds to an independent propagation matrix $\mathbf{S}^{(k)}$, rather than iteratively applying the same matrix. While each $\mathbf{S}^{(k)}$ may have a stationary distribution,

they are different for different k . There is no single limiting operator that erases all feature information. This fundamentally differs from the implicit layer-by-layer accumulation of near-neighbors through $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^k$ in traditional GNNs, which inherently assume homophilic relationships. It implies that OPP no longer requires a strong correlation between the center node and its immediate neighbors. The toy heatmap in Fig.S3 shows an example. Even as the propagation iterations increase, the OPP approximation of the dilated convolution effect avoids convergence between representations. Because $\mathbf{S}^{(k)}$ represents the relationship of k -hop neighbors, rather than continuous propagation k times. Therefore, when k is larger than the diameter of the graph, $\mathbf{S}^{(k)}$ may be a very sparse matrix.

Path aware mechanism. Although shortest pathways can reveal beneficial gene associations, they are insufficient to reflect refined interactions. On the one hand, genes involved in more pathways are more likely to exhibit synergies that a single path cannot support. On the other hand, it weakens the association between genes with more pathway interactions because the OPP retains only their shortest pathways. All genes in the same parallel channel $\mathbf{B}^{(k)}$ will be treated as equally influential.

To take advantage of the composite role of genes in multiple signaling pathways, we further design a path aware mechanism to quantify the strength of cooperation between genes:

$$\alpha_{ij}^{(k)} = \sum_{\ell=k}^K [\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(\ell)}]_{ij}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (6)$$

where K is a hyperparameter denoting the maximum path length. Here, $\alpha_{ij}^{(k)}$ maps the sum of diffusion weights contributed by all paths longer than the shortest distance k between node pairs v_i and v_j . The interaction score generated for each path is determined by the degree of the nodes passing through that path. The design is inspired by urban transportation networks and coincides with existing biological views: 1) There are more routes to essential hubs, such as the city center; 2) Intersections frequently traversed by multiple routes between two locations tend to be far more critical than others; 3) Congestion at key intersections may lead to overall traffic collapse.

In addition, by tracing the original gene pathway relationships, the a priori biological knowledge (e.g., protein interactions) embedded in the network will also be incorporated to underpin the prediction of cancer genes. However, current methods rarely use them as an aid to prediction. Besides the above observation, Equation (3) shows that the contribution of too-long pathways is attenuated, which agrees with the empirical consistency of the signaling cascade length, ensuring biological plausibility. Subsequently, $\alpha_{ij}^{(k)}$ is combined with OPP. The connection relationships recorded in $\mathbf{S}^{(k)}$ are regarded as compressed virtual edges, where the weight of any edge reflects the biological relevance score obtained by extracting the original arbitrary pair of gene topological relationships. Therefore, the proposed propagation block in Eq. (3) can be formulated as follows:

$$\mathbf{P}_{ij}^{(k)} = \mathbf{S}_{ij}^{(k)} \alpha_{ij}^{(k)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{H}^k = \mathbf{P}^{(k)} \mathbf{H}^0 \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{Z} = \left\{ \mathbf{H}^0, \underbrace{\mathbf{H}^{(1)}, \mathbf{H}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{H}^{(K)}}_{\text{Isolated K-order channel}} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{H}^k represents the gene representation matrix of the k -th channel. Unlike the previous iterative computation of \mathbf{H}^{k-1} based on \mathbf{H}^k , here the initial node representation \mathbf{H}^0 is propagated simultaneously over all K -order channels in “one step” to form a parallel gene representation set \mathbf{Z} . In this case, each representation $\mathbf{H}^{(k)}$ is derived from a separate propagation matrix. It does not converge to a constant as k changes, thus forming a parallel set of gene representations \mathbf{Z} .

GPR weights fuse local to global representations. To balance local and global information, we incorporate generalized pagerank factors to adaptively reweight each channel in \mathbf{Z} . The final fused embedding of gene nodes is computed as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{Z}} = \sum_{k=0}^K \gamma^k \mathbf{H}^{(k)} = \sum_{k=0}^K \gamma^k \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{S}^{(k)} \odot \alpha^{(k)} \right)}_{\mathbf{P}^{(k)}} \mathbf{H}^{(0)} \quad (10)$$

where \odot represents the Hadamard product and γ is similar to the classic solution of the personalized PageRank (PPR) coefficient at the beginning of training:

$$\gamma^k = \beta(1 - \beta)^k, \quad \beta \in (0, 1) \quad (11)$$

where β is an empirically set initial coefficient and the final representation $\bar{\mathbf{Z}}$ carries multi-scale information from first-order local to K -order global. The learnable GPR coefficients permit the model to reweight different hop-orders during training, including the possibility of positive or negative contributions, so that the network can adaptively emphasise or attenuate information coming from specific distances. This flexibility is better suited to accommodate heterophilic signal distributions encountered in biological networks and for tracking the specific contributions of propagation orders to prediction.

More deeply, compared with classical GPR, which employs the transition matrix $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ as its basis filters, we emphasise more biologically informed basis filters $\mathbf{P}^{(k)}$ derived from OPP and pathway awareness. This makes the optimization of γ^k dependent on these propagation operators’ behavior within the cancer gene context and the underlying network structure. As a result, representations from different hops can trade off consistency and diversity during end-to-end biological context, thereby enriching the expressive power of the entire model.

Task objectives and model training. For given gene node features and partial labels \mathbf{y} , CGMap focuses on the cancer gene prediction task with unbalanced classification. The overall model is trained in an end-to-end manner, where the training objective combines two complementary loss functions: binary cross-entropy loss and focal loss. The composite loss function is as follows:

$$\mathcal{L} = \theta \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}} + (1 - \theta) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{Focal}} \quad (12)$$

where θ is a hyperparameter used for balancing. Specifically, To counteract label distribution skewness and further address hard misclassified examples, we formalize \mathcal{L}_{BCE} and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{Focal}}$ as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}} = - \sum_{v_i \in \mathcal{V}_m} \omega_{\text{pos}} \cdot \mathbf{y}_i \log(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i) + (1 - \mathbf{y}_i) \log(1 - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_i) \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Focal}} = - \sum_{v_i \in \mathcal{V}_m} \begin{cases} \mu \cdot (1 - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_i)^\gamma \log(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i), & \text{if } y_i = 1 \\ (1 - \mu) \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i)^\gamma \log(1 - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_i), & \text{if } y_i = 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{y}_i is obtained by inputting a fused multiscale representation into the Sigmoid classifier. $\mathcal{V}_m \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ denotes the set of labeled nodes in the training set. To offset the skewness of the label distributions, we quantitatively compensate for different classes by a regularization factor ω_{pos} based on the difference in the proportion of positive and negative samples. In addition, Focal Loss will focus on the convergence of difficult samples to further improve the discrimination of samples with low confidence. The hyperparameters μ and γ control the category weights and the decay rate of easily categorized samples, respectively. This hybrid design simultaneously addresses both macroscopic class imbalance and microscopic hard example mining. During training, we monitor the evolution of graph propagation weights through exponential moving average recording, enabling interpretable analysis of learned message-passing dynamics.

4.3 Implementation details

We implemented all methods using a consistent training and data-splitting workflow, employing ten repeats of 5-fold cross-validation and reporting average performance to ensure fairness. For evaluation under imbalanced data, we use the area under the ROC curve (AUC) and the area under the precision-recall curve (AUPR) as evaluation metrics. The experimental environment was conducted in Python 3.8 with PyTorch 1.12.1, PyTorch Geometric 2.6.1, and CUDA 11.3 on a workstation equipped with an Intel[®] Xeon[®] E5-2683 v4 CPU and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 GPU (24 GB).

To achieve the best performance for each model, we perform a hyperparameter search through Optuna based on Bayesian optimization and evolutionary strategies [100]. The training process uses Adam as the optimizer. For the CGMap maximum layers K , we search from 1 to 10 with a step size of 1. The learning rate is adjusted from $5e - 4$ to $2e - 2$, and the dropout rate is searched from 0 to 1. For different datasets, we independently adjust the number of training epochs from 100 to 3000 and set the early stopping strategy. The weight decay is tuned from $6e - 4$ to $2e - 2$. The model’s hidden layer dimensions are tuned mainly in 64 to 512. In addition, the hyperparameters μ and θ in the loss function are chosen from 0-1 in steps of 0.05. γ is tuned in the range of 1 to 10. It is worth noting that the longest reachable path between gene nodes is directly limited to 10. According to the “small world” principle, it covers almost any graph.

4.4 Baselines

We selected 12 representative models in four main categories as baselines for comparison, covering classical methods for GNNs, novel designs, deep architectures, and customized frameworks for the cancer gene task. They have shown state-of-the-art performance in multiple graph representation learning and biological tasks.

1. The classical GNNs: GCN, GAT, Chebnet, and GATv2.
 - GCN** [25]. A standard method for first-order approximation of spectral graph filters and learning node representations from near neighbors information.
 - GAT** [26]. Pioneering graph attention network with static self-attention among node neighbors derived from GCN.
 - Chebnet** [27]. A scalable spectral graph convolution using Chebyshev polynomial approximation, which partially facilitates information propagation among multiple hops.
 - GATv2** [28]. Vanilla GAT-derived enhanced dynamic attention variants.
2. Some advanced designed GNNs: ARMAGNN, TAGCN, PMLP, and AGNN.
 - ARMAGNN** [29]. A spectral filter incorporating an autoregressive moving average filter captures frequency response on graphs.
 - TAGCN** [30]. A Topology-Adaptive framework with a set of learnable polynomial filters is employed for local feature extraction while avoiding linear approximation.
 - PMLP** [31]. An implicit message passing baseline with pure MLPs as training backbone and performing graph propagation only at inference time.
 - AGNN** [32]. An attention propagation model combining node embedding similarity and local structural dependencies.
3. The Deep GNN Architecture: JKNet.
 - JKNet** [33]. A variant of residual connection, “jump connection”, is proposed to aggregate representations of neighborhoods across deep layers by combining or pooling.
4. Customized methods for cancer gene: EMOGI, MTGCN, and CGMega.
 - EMOGI** [10]. The model combines GNNs with multi-omics data and performs biological graph analysis through an external interpretable block.
 - MTGCN** [12]. A multi-task optimization framework for simultaneous cancer gene classification and link prediction.
 - CGMega** [11]. A cancer gene module parsing framework that integrates Transformer and GAT and introduces GNNexplainer to assist in interpretation.

In more detail, these baselines include fundamental spectral or spatial design paradigms, multiple different attention mechanisms, adaptive filtering, staged or hierarchical processing, and domain-specific graph learning advancements.

5 Data availability

All data supporting our findings are publicly available, and a detailed list can be accessed directly via the following github repositories: <https://github.com/Incendio1/CGMap>. Downstream benchmarks for cancer gene backgrounds are primarily from the original paper, and other graph representation learning benchmarks are available

at https://github.com/pyg-team/pytorch_geometric. Additionally, the Optuna v4/v5 framework for automated hyperparameter search can be found at <https://github.com/optuna/optuna>. The candidate cancer genes cohort were taken from NCG7.2, http://network-cancer-genes.org/candidate_drivers.php. Data sources used to validate novel cancer genes include GEPIA2 (<http://gepia2.cancer-pku.cn>), TIMER (<https://compbio.cn/timer3>), GSCA (<https://guolab.wchscu.cn/GSCA>), and CancerSEA (<http://biocc.hrbmu.edu.cn/CancerSEA>). Data preparation and preprocessing refer to <https://github.com/schulter/EMOGI>.

6 Code availability

The source code of CGMap is available in gitHub repository, which supports the reproduction of experimental results: <https://github.com/Incendio1/CGMap>.

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Author contributions

C.W. and M.L. conceptualized the work. C.W. implemented the model and algorithm. C.W., Y.Z., and X.S. collected the data. C.W. and X.S. conducted the experiments. C.W. and X.S. plotted figures. C.W. prepared the manuscript. C.W., L.T., and M.L. revised the manuscript. M.L. supervised the research and conducted the code review.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.